

EARTH SCIENCES

APPLICATIONS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TO PREDICT THE LIKELIHOOD OF EARTHQUAKES BASED ON MAGNETO-GRAVIMETRIC AND HYDRO-GEOCHEMICAL MEASUREMENTS

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Abstract

The paper proposes a method for using Artificial Intelligence to predict the likelihood of an earthquake. Based on the observation of changes in the energy states of various geophysical (magneto-gravimetric) and hydro-geochemical fields, the probability of an earthquake is assessed. This approach to solving prognostic problems using Artificial Intelligence is being considered, when each moment in time can be compared with many categories of events occurring in a given place on Earth. Events can be deterministic or random in nature. In the general case, the system of determination of any event includes both deterministic and random components in various proportions.

Keywords: earthquakes, likelihood, prediction, artificial intelligence.

An earthquake is a physical process of release and redistribution energy in the earth's crust and mantle, which occurs under the influence of enormous forces. Regarding these forces, today it is hypothetically known that they arise during the rise of mantle material in oceanic ridges, which, gradually cooling and moving along the surface of the earth, interact with existing tectonic plates. At the same time, the stress-strain state of the earth's crust changes and in places where the strength reaches critical values, microcracks begin to appear, which eventually combine into a directional crack in the form of an earthquake.

Scientists have long been studying the stress-strain state in laboratories, conducting experiments on the rupture of various structurally inhomogeneous materials, with the aim of applying the experimental results to the modeling of tectonic processes [1]. Despite progress in this area, predictions of critical situations are still extremely inaccurate. There are many reasons for forecast inaccuracy. Earthquakes, unlike individual physical phenomena, cannot be separated from many other processes operating simultaneously. There are more than 1000 different signs that in certain situations can be taken as harbingers of strong earthquakes.

Unfortunately, a 100% such sign does not exist today. Depending on the situation, one or another sign works or does not work. It is also not always possible to recognize why these signs fail. Existing forecast work earthquakes can be grouped into four categories according to the methodologies applied: mathematical models, earthquake precursor monitoring, recognition-based machine learning algorithms and deep learning.

Mathematical modeling formulates the problem of earthquake prediction using methods of continuum mechanics and various approaches of probability theory. The second category is represented by work on detecting earthquake precursors. Namely, changes in geotectonic parameters of the earth's surface, electromagnetic, geochemical anomalies and anomalies in the speed of seismic waves and similar deviations of signals from the average value. The fourth category includes pattern

recognition and deep learning algorithms that predict the location and approximate time of strong earthquakes. Unlike standard prediction methods, artificial intelligence combines all kinds of existing disparate data, compares them and tries to find the most likely solution to the issue [2].

During an earthquake, colossal energy is released in the earth's crust $M=23(\lg \frac{E}{10^7} - 4,8)$, $ML = 2/3(\lg E - 4,8)$, here E — is an earthquake energy in joules, ML is a magnitude of the earthquake at the epicenter. This energy gradually accumulates in the periods preceding the shock and is released (usually gradually) after the shock. This energy, before and after the shock, propagates through the Earth's crust in the form of acoustic (seismic) and electromagnetic waves, causing variations in the values of various geophysical (magneto-gravimetric) and hydro-geochemical parameters of geological structures [3,4]. The primary causes of earthquakes can be either internal processes, such as the movement of tectonic plates, or external ones, related to the movement of cosmic objects, primarily the Sun and the Moon. Here, it is necessary to consider both the direct and inverse problems.

Direct problem: an earthquake occurs, and the resulting seismic energy is expended on changing the energy states of various geophysical (geomagnetic E_M , gravitational E_G , radiation E_R , etc.) and hydro-geochemical fields (ionic composition and chemical properties of artesian waters).

$$\frac{dE_0}{dt} = \frac{\partial E_M}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial E_G}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial E_R}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial E_{CH}}{\partial t} \dots$$

In this case, it's relatively easy to visually track these correlations.

The inverse problem (predictive): we observe changes in the energy states of various geophysical and/or hydro-geochemical fields. However, this phenomenon can be caused by both internal terrestrial processes (movement of tectonic plates) and processes occurring on the Sun (solar storms), as well as the relative

motion (phases and antiphase) of the Earth, Moon, and Sun. In this case, a complex, integrated analysis is required, taking into account as many internal terrestrial and external cosmic factors as possible.

Let's also consider another approach to solving prognostic problems using Artificial Intelligence. Each moment in time can be associated with multiple categories of events occurring at a given location on Earth. Events can be deterministic or random. Generally, the system for determining any event includes both deterministic and random components in varying proportions. For this, we use the method proposed in the paper [5].

To establish a pattern in a sequence of events and describe it as a function, it can be compared with another sequence or set of sequences, which is considered as the argument of this function. The problem of recognizing event categories can be formulated using deterministic sequences. A special case of this problem is recognizing event categories from seismic data.

Let's assume a set of events A, which corresponds to a set of categories C_i . An event can be considered an earthquake recorded by a seismological station, and a category can be considered its magnitude, which lies within a certain interval, and the hypocenter depth. Each earthquake event is characterized by a time and the geographic coordinates of its origin. Using this data, we can construct a matrix containing variations in certain geophysical or hydro-geochemical quantities, such as the magnitude of the geomagnetic or gravitational field, or the radon content in the near-surface region.

We assume that frequency distributions N_i is the number of events related to a given category C_i are given. We determine the number of occurrences of this category within a given interval of change in geophysical/hydro-geochemical parameters, i.e., in the discrete case, we have:

$$N_{ij}(x_j, k) = N_i w(\tilde{x}_j, k) \Delta x, x_j < \tilde{x}_j < x_j + \Delta x \quad (1)$$

$$1 \leq i \leq n, 1 \leq j \leq 2m, k = 1, \dots, k_0$$

Here: w is the event distribution density along the normalized coordinate (1). The normalized variable is defined through the angular and radial coordinates of the epicenter from the measurement points on the earth's surface as follows:

$$x_{jk} = \begin{cases} \frac{\vartheta_0(k)}{2\pi}, & 1 \leq j \leq m \\ \frac{r_{max}(k) - r(k)}{r_{max}(k) - r_{min}(k)}, & m + 1 \leq j \leq 2m \end{cases}$$

where r_{min} and r_{max} are the minimum and maximum distances of the measurement point from the epicenter, and k_0 is the number of geophysical/hydro-geochemical parameters used in the problem.

Let's define the information matrix according to:

$$\frac{N_{ij}}{\sum_j N_{ij}} I_{ijk} = \log_2 \frac{N_{ij} / \sum_j N_{ij}}{\sum_j N_{ij} / \sum_{i,j} N_{ij}}, N_{ij}(x_{jk}) \neq 0$$

$$I_{ijk} = 0, N_{ij}(x_{jk}) = 0,$$

$$\delta I_{jk} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_i \left(I_{ijk} - \frac{1}{n} \sum_i I_{ijk} \right)^2}, 1 \leq i \leq n, 1 \leq j \leq 2m, 1 \leq k \leq k_0 \quad (2)$$

The first value (2) is called the informativeness of the feature (factor value), and the second value is the standard deviation of the informativeness, or the integral informativeness. Each category can be associated with a vector of informativeness of astronomical parameters of dimension $2mk_0$, composed of elements of the informativeness matrix by sequentially writing the columns corresponding to the normalized coordinate into a single column, i.e.

$$C_{is} = I_{ijk} |_{ik=s}, 1 \leq s \leq 2mk_0 \quad (3)$$

On the other hand, the process of identification and recognition can be considered as the decomposition of the vector of the recognizable object into a series of vectors of categories (recognition classes) [5]. This vector, consisting of ones and zeros, can be determined by the coordinates of celestial bodies corresponding to the date and place of origin of the event l in the form

$$a_{ls} = \begin{cases} 1, & (j-1)\Delta x \leq x_{jk}(l) \leq j\Delta x, jk = s \\ 0, & 1 \leq s \leq 2mk_0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Thus, if the normalized coordinate of a celestial body from the data for the object of the studied sample falls within the specified interval, the vector element is assigned the value 1, and in all other cases, the value 0. The listing of coordinates is carried out sequentially, for each celestial body.

If the system of vectors (3) is complete, any vector (4) can be represented as a linear combination of vectors in system (3). The coefficients of this decomposition will correspond to the level of similarity of a given event with a given category. If the system of vectors (3) is incomplete, the exact procedure is replaced by recognition. In this case, the level of similarity of the event data with a given category can be determined by the magnitude of the scalar product of vector (4) and vector (3), i.e.

$$K_{il} = \frac{1}{|a_{il}||c_{il}|} \sum_{s=1}^{2mk_0} a_{ls}(A) c_{is} \quad (5)$$

Note that there are four possible outcomes for which a given event can be assigned or not assigned to a given category, either correctly or falsely. To account for these outcomes, category recognition in the artificial intelligence system is performed using a similarity parameter, which is defined as follows [5]:

$$S_i = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{l=1}^N (BT_{il} + T_{il} - BF_{il} - F_{il}) \cdot 100\% \quad (6)$$

Here,

S_i – is a reliability of identification of the "i-th" category;

N – is a number of events in the recognizable sample;

BT_{il} – is the level of similarity of the “l-th” event with the “i-th” category to which it was correctly assigned by the system;

T_{il} – is the level of similarity of the “l-th” event with the “i-th” category to which it was not correctly assigned by the system;

BF_{il} – is the level of similarity of the “l-th” event with the “i-th” category to which it was mistakenly assigned by the system;

F_{il} – the level of similarity of the “l-th” event with the “i-th” category to which it was erroneously not assigned by the system.

With this definition, the similarity parameter ranges from -100% to 100%, like a typical correlation coefficient in statistics. Obviously, the similarity parameter must satisfy the simple test criterion

$$S_i(N=1) = 100\%$$

The similarity parameter recognition procedure (6), implemented in the artificial intelligence system, is robust to both sample size and the number of model cells. The reason why it is possible to identify subsets (categories) of events of varying, even random, nature using geophysical (magneto-gravimetric) and hydro-geochemical parameters is quite obvious. In some cases, this is sufficient for category recognition. This

problem can be compared to the Kalman filtering procedure for filtering a stream of electromagnetic signals (electrical pulses). This recursive filter estimates the state vector of a dynamic system using a series of incomplete, noisy measurements (background, noise signals are superimposed on the useful signal).

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